

Impact Factor: 8.67

ISSN:0976-8165

THE CRITERION

AN INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL IN ENGLISH

Bi-Monthly Peer-Reviewed eJournal

16 YEARS OF OPEN ACCESS

VOL. 16 ISSUE-4, AUGUST 2025

Editor-In-Chief: **Dr. Vishwanath Bite**
Managing Editor: **Dr. Madhuri Bite**

www.the-criterion.com

AboutUs: <http://www.the-criterion.com/about/>

Archive: <http://www.the-criterion.com/archive/>

ContactUs: <http://www.the-criterion.com/contact/>

EditorialBoard: <http://www.the-criterion.com/editorial-board/>

Submission: <http://www.the-criterion.com/submission/>

FAQ: <http://www.the-criterion.com/fa/>

ISSN 2278-9529

Galaxy: International Multidisciplinary Research Journal
www.galaxyimrj.com

Politics of Transgression in the Novels of Arundhati Roy

Dr. Shweta Kumari

Assistant Professor,
Department of English,
Purnea Mahila Mahavidyalaya, Purnia.

Dr. Pinaki Ranjan Das

Assistant Professor,
Department of English,
PG Department of English,
Purnea University, Purnea.

Article History: Submitted-13/07/2025, Revised-04/08/2025, Accepted-09/08/2025, Published-31/08/2025.

Abstract:

Politics and literature can be seen as complementary to each other. The political conditions shape an author and the literature of the time, and influential literature is able to bring about political changes with its affective power. The aim of literature has been considered differently at different times, but no one can deny its effect on social and political thinking and the mind's working. Starting from Addison, Steel, Swift, Pope, Tennyson, Dickens, Ibsen, Brecht, and George Orwell in English Literature to Rabindranath Tagore, Aurobindo Ghose, Mulk Raj Anand, Khushwant Singh, Bapsi Sidhwa, Shashi Tharoor, and Salman Rushdie in Indian English Literature, almost all have acknowledged the political potential of a work of art and negotiated it very aptly.

Arundhati Roy is one of the activist writers of the present time who writes with a strong political accent. As a matter of fact, she has written only two novels, and others of her writings belong to the critical essay genre on various social-political topics. However, her fiction is no less political in its address. She has underlined multiple

forms of injustice imposed upon the powerless section of society. She never misses her mark in pointing out the political aid gained by the powerful to justify their authority. Her novels vividly portray subordination and depict the transgression strategy adopted by the powerless to answer back. Her novels are the novels of dissent. The present paper aims to provide an analysis of transgression politics as exercised by the subaltern. It will also try to assess the strength of transgression in addressing prejudice and discrimination prevalent in society and seeking social justice for marginalised people.

Keywords: transgression, politics, marginalized, identity, love-laws, societal norms.

Aristotle, in his work *Politics*, defines man as a political animal by nature. Politics encompasses art, activity, and thought aimed at improving living conditions and negotiating power distribution among different groups within a society. Societies operate according to the specific codes, conduct, and norms. What benefits one group may not be advantageous to others, necessitating the search for solutions. The solutions chosen by certain groups may lead to disagreements based on the acceptance or rejection of the ideas. Therefore, politics is an essential activity, characterized by numerous disagreements and diverse solutions. It is primarily concerned with society and serves as a form of social dialogue.

Politics can be defined from various perspectives, depending on the context and our points of view. It can be seen as a complex set of actions within a particular social framework, or as an academic subject that studies these actions. For this discussion, we are primarily interested in politics as a complex set of actions. The term “politics” can also be interpreted as a verb in two different ways. On one hand, it can be seen as the art of governing people. This authority is not limited to the government but includes any institution that creates rules within a social unit, such as culture, language, tradition, economy, and

history. These aspects of society help in establishing rules and norms for society to function smoothly. On the other hand, politics can be viewed as an act of public affairs. The discussion of politics as a form of government cannot be completed without addressing politics as a concern of public social affairs. Public affairs and common people are subject to the politics created by the ruling institutions. Even the smallest unit of society, such as a family, is not exempt from politics, as it can influence and be influenced by those who make the rules. Nothing, from a club to a community gathering, is free from politics, making it all-encompassing.

As we know, political discourse is grounded in disagreements. Even an ideal political environment may prove to be oppressive for many. In a power relation, one decision cannot satisfy the whole. Perhaps here comes the Hegelian logic of the dialectical basis of systems and institutions. The seemingly seamless structure of society is fraught with acts of resistance and overstepping. The act of transgression always aims at redefining the limits, boundaries and margins of the presumably solid structure. This structure, which we call society, is hard to define because it is an amalgamation of various thoughts, beliefs, ideas, cultures, institutions and communities. However, any of these elements are not all-encompassing and attract our attention to their limits and centres. They are secured with some definite norms, rules and codes of conduct to strengthen the centre and these norms give them a somewhat tangible identity. Nevertheless, we know that identity is a process of doing and undoing, learning and forgetting, and, sustaining and going beyond. “To transgress is to go beyond the bounds or limits set by a commandment or law or convention, it is to violate or infringe” (Jenks 2). In doing so, transgression also informs the members about the limits of the conventions of the society. It maps the social order, and its direction of change in terms of growth or stagnation.

As the paper will concern itself with the works of a contemporary author who discusses the challenges of postcolonial society in India, we first need to have a basic understanding of this society. As previously mentioned, society requires a center, order, and fundamental belief worth defending for concepts such as transgression and resistance to hold meaning. The problem with this postmodern society, as Durkheim explains, is that it is based on organic solidarity, where everyone is mutually dependent (Durkheim, *Division* 68). Its agents, when they transgress, cannot be punished in the traditional sense, which was popular in traditional societies based on mechanical solidarity. However, it is very challenging to put Indian society in this binary of either/or. Indian culture is complex. It participates in the global market and is influenced by modernity, but it also maintains feudal and traditional ideologies within its communities. Like any society, there is a visible divide between the powerful and powerless sections. Since no society is perfect enough to capture and accommodate every single individuality there is always a possibility of individual divergence, dissolution, dissent or difference (Jenks 41). The powerless group, who lay at the margins, adopts many devices to bring out its suppressed voice and secure justice for itself. Hence, not just the act of transgression but its reception as well is a point to study in the case of Indian society.

In this paper, we are mainly concerned with the politics of transgression and its importance in voicing social injustice against common people. It is generally defined as an act of going against the law, rules, norms, tradition and code of conduct. The present paper will examine the novels *The God of Small Things (TGST)* and *The Ministry of Utmost Happiness (TMUH)* by Arundhati Roy to find out the presentation of transgression as depicted in the texts. As a novelist, she crafts a wonderfully magical, vast area of diverse experiences and emotions, allowing her readers to engage in multiple perspectives, valuing each point of view equally for discussion. Sometimes it is a feminist novel, sometimes a Dalit

and on other occasions, a political one. She has raised her voice against the suppressing laws of the society, of which class, caste and gender issues are only some to name. Through apparently simple storylines, she gradually reveals different dimensions of social reality and critiques them one by one.

Roy represents a world of “Big Man the Laltain” and “Small Man the Mombatti”. The larger, more powerful individuals, referred to as the Laltain men, exploit and mistreat the Mombattis in various ways. Through the characters of Ammu, Velutha, Estha, and Rahel in *TGST* and Anjum, Tilo, Saddam Hussain, Ms Jabeen, Naga and Zainab in *TMUH*, the narrative unfolds the harsh realities of patriarchy, the caste system, gender, politics, and the legal system in society. Roy highlights the struggles and the will of the oppressed to assert themselves and speak out against injustice. The novels portray how traditional norms, history, culture, and law and order often work against the marginalized sections of society. The characters’ acts of moral, conventional and sexual transgression symbolize rebellion and become their means of challenging injustice, despite leading to dire consequences.

Dissatisfactions with metanarratives characterise the present postmodern and postcolonial culture. Nietzsche has already presented an obituary to the Almighty, signifying there cannot be any certainty, any absolute truth or value that can control the universe. Transgression as a politics raises questions against such metanarratives, hierarchies and identity formations. Patriarchy is one such framework that regulates the identities and conduct of individuals in a society. In *TGST*, living in a conservative patriarchal family, Ammu learns “that you can’t trust anybody. Mother, father, brother, husband, bestfriend. Nobody (*TGST* 83).” She witnessed her mother being abused by her father, a respected figure in society, who transformed into a monster when arguing with Mammachi. At times, Ammu also endured this brutality. “As she grew older, Ammu learned to live with this cold, calculating cruelty. She developed a lofty sense of injustice and the mulish, reckless streak

that develops in Someone Small who has been bullied all their lives by Someone Big (*TGST* 181)". In a similar vein, *TMUH* portrays characters in various socially and politically challenging situations. Anjum's story vividly depicts the struggle of a transgender person in a patriarchal society. Being a transgender person, her position is seen as 'not normal' and it was the only available social, cultural and political identity that she could avail. "For societies, as for individuals, health is good and desirable; sickness, on the other hand, is bad and must be avoided (Durkheim, *Division* 84)." The distinction between healthy and sick is made based on irregular and different. The body of a transgender is thus treated as a sick body when compared to the able bodies. This difference results in seclusion and denial of rights. Anjum is not accepted in her patriarchal society and family and is migrated to live with other transgender people (which is not a homogeneous category) in Khwabgah. However, even Khwabgah cannot ensure happiness for these social outcasts. Nimmo tells Anjum

'No one's happy here. It's not possible. Arre yaar, think about it, what are the things you normal people get unhappy about?... Price-rise, children's school-admissions, husbands' beatings, wives' cheatings, Hindu-Muslim riots, Indo-Pak war – outside things that settle down eventually. But for us The riot is inside us. The war is inside us. Indo-Pak is inside us. It will never settle down. It can't.' (*TMUH* 23)

The act of transgression must redefine social practices and give new meanings to identities. If that is denied, it can hardly be called a transgressive act. We need to understand that transgression does not aim to provide a parallel system of hegemony that operates from multiple hierarchies. In this sense, it is different from hegemonic resistance (Foust 2). Ammu's decision to choose a husband of her own choice, outside her Syrian Christian community, is still committing herself to a parallel system of oppression. After the divorce,

Ammu returns to Ayemenem. Not to mention she received a cold welcome at her own home. “Within the first few months of her return to her parents’ home, Ammu quickly learned to recognize and despise the ugly face of sympathy. Old female relations with incipient beards and several wobbling chins made overnight trips to Ayemenem to commiserate with her about her divorce. They squeezed her knee and gloated. She fought off the urge to slap them (*TGST* 43)”. Here she realizes that a woman does not have a ‘Locusts Stand I’. She has to work according to the wishes of Mammachi, Baby Kochamma, Chocko and everyone else. Different members of the family receive different responses. Different rules are applied to the children of the same house depending on gender and place in hierarchical order. Similarly, Anjum's choice to leave her family and live with the people of Khwabgah could not change her fate, as Khwabgah is simply another parallel system with its own societal and familial hierarchies to adhere to. Initially, Anjum was happy and felt loved by Ustad Kulsoom Bi, the head of this family. She initially didn't believe Nimmo's warnings about the realities of life as a Hijra in Khwabgah. However, soon Anjum's body started showing changes, and the harsh reality of her new life became apparent. She found it very hard to come to terms with her changed position in Khwabgah, where there are new recruits all the time, and she is no longer in demand. She “lived in the Khwabgah with her patched-together body and her partially realized dreams for more than thirty years (*TMUH* 29) before she moved out of this house to create her own world.

The act of transgression can be seen as an alternative way to exist in a society. It allows individuals to express their dissatisfaction with a social structure that is unfriendly to marginalized groups and creates a space for them to exist. However, this position is inherently unsafe and leaves the individual vulnerable within the social framework. The transgressive act is particularly punishable when committed by the minority and powerless individuals. *TGST* explores the forbidden love between Ammu and Velutha, which was

suppressed by the communists at Ayemenem House in Kerala. This illicit love is paralleled by the relationship between Baby Kochamma and Father Mulligan, as well as the forbidden romance of Chacko and the female factory workers. The novel highlights how not all transgressions are punished equally, as power dynamics play a significant role in the consequences. Baby Kochamma gives up her struggle and pursues other interests (she has given in to the wishes of the family and society), while Chacko is allowed to indulge in excess due to class and gender. On the other side, there's Velutha, an untouchable Paravan who is skilled in carpentry and machines. He is an educated person with an air of self-respect which makes him vulnerable in an orthodox society. When rehired at the factory, other workers were unhappy, highlighting how caste outweighs class. Unlike others, Velutha believes in challenging his fate. His talent and spirit of a struggler made him transgress the borders created by society for an untouchable. He worked in Chacko's factory, he was allowed to enter Ayemenem House from the back, and he is a cardholding member of the Communist party. However, all these favours were done within a field of compromises, so that he must remember he is an untouchable. In *TMUH*, Anjum is vulnerable in society because of her gender. She could not continue her formal education; she could not have a proper family or a respectable job and she was denied any claim of motherhood. They could not even ask for respect as a human being. They are exploited by the police from time to time. When contemplating about an incident of one night and their encounter with police, she could only remember the humiliation. "True, it was only a routine bit of humiliation for Hijras, nothing out of the ordinary, and nothing at all compared to the tribulations others endured during those horrible months (*TMUH* 35). However, it is interesting to note that the gender identity which excludes her from the society also saves her during a massacre in Gujarat as it brings bad luck if a hijra is killed. Anjum is unable to make sense of such *Duniya*. This trauma brought her near to madness, and she tried to restore her sanity by

forsaking the *Duniya*, where she could not learn how to exist. The novel *TMUH* is written twenty years after Roy's first novel, but she never fails to show that caste is still a vulnerable position for people to exist in a society. We are amazed to notice how caste plays a more crucial role in society where people exist on the verge of orthodoxy. In this novel, Saddam Hussain, a friend of Anjum, is tortured to the point of his conversion to Islam. He was primarily a Dalit who was struggling to get a fixed job. His father was lynched on account of the charges of 'cow slaughter' and he too was attacked brutally but survived. He knows the caste politics and says 'they accuse you of eating beef and then take over your house and your land and send you to a refugee camp. It's all about property, not cows' (402). After that, he gave up on the religion that could not accept or protect him and renamed himself 'Saddam Hussain'.

Defying social norms often leads to a sense of loneliness for individuals. This precarious situation inevitably puts the marginalized people at the margins of everything in society. The very idea of centre and margin operates by the principle of 'identity politics. Since authority is predominantly held by those in power, they create a face of society that relies on difference for its existence and hence the prevalent binaries in a society. If we take Durkheimian symbolism into account, the society is divided into the sacred and the profane. They are not just two realms rather two value-specific territories with distinct boundaries. The relationship between them is one of tension. "The sacred may be seen to represent public knowledge and social institutions, and the profane to represent the potential of individual consciousness – it is that which is always threatening to bring down the sacred (Jenks 29)". Arundhati Roy effectively illustrates this anxiety surrounding social identity in her work, equipping her characters with individual consciousness and the capacity to act, even if these actions ultimately lead to tragic outcomes. The characters of Roy often grapple with profound

solitude that isolates them from mainstream society. Yet, this solitude also allows them space for introspection and forging unique identities beyond societal expectations.

Ammu and Velutha (in *TGST*) live in an orthodox society where the line between the sacred and the profane is maintained religiously. In such a conservatively guarded society Ammu and Velutha desire for each other. They both knew the consequences yet proceeded, "... they broke the Love Laws that lay down who should be loved. And how. And how much". Both were doomed for their act of love. Velutha was killed brutally and Ammu was left alone by all to wait for her death. Anjum also chooses to stay alone in the graveyard, where she can find a strange comfort. She is not haunted here by the ghost or memories instead she feels a sameness with the atmosphere. Here, loneliness is intertwined with the solitude of the graveyard, and she finds a sense of belongingness. The graveyard mirrors her internal world which is full of unfulfilled desires, personal tragedies and traumas. However, it is also a place where she is able to explore her true self and history that society tries to suppress. Here she learns to navigate the social landscape. She realises here that the life she has led is full of humiliations and perseverance but this also gave her strength to go on, ultimately empowering her.

In the next instance, love laws were transgressed by Estha and Rahel. Their desire for each other's bodies made them break the law of incest imposed by history. From the very start, we are given a hint about the rebellion of Rahel and Estha. They were dizygotic twins and introduced by the novelist as "the emptiness in one twin was only a version of the quietness in the other. That the two things fitted together. Like stacked spoons. Like familiar lovers' bodies" (*TGST* 20). Rahel and Estha have been separated from each other since their childhood. This loss of relation, which existed even before their life began, brought nothingness within them. Rahel turned out to be a nihilist and Estha became a nonexistent

entity. Their desire for each other was necessary to make others believe in his/her existence. They broke the love laws to find themselves.

We have other transgressors too in the novel. Baby Kochamma who loved Father Mulligan leads a life of celibacy that is forbidden for women in her religion. She denied bringing anyone else into her life and only Father Mulligan's memories can intrude into her thoughts. Though not accepted by society and religion, she fantasises about Mulligan after his death as her life partner, in a plane where physicality dissolves. Next, we have Chacko the Oxford returned scholar, a well-acclaimed communist who works for the poor. He also married outside his religion but was forgiven by his family first because he was a man and second because he chose an English Christian as his life partner. When Margaret Kochamma left Chocko, he returned to India and started satisfying his 'man's need' through his illegal romance with factory workers' wives. However, contrary to the reaction gained by Ammu-Velutha's love affair, Chocko was supported by both Baby Kochamma and Mammachi. These latter two instances of transgression were committed by powerful members of society and did not provoke backlash from others.

Perhaps Ammu, Estha and she were the worst transgressors. But it wasn't just them. It was the others too. They all broke the rules. They all crossed into forbidden territory. They all tampered with the laws that lay down who should be loved and how. And how much. The laws that make grandmothers grandmothers, uncles uncles, mothers mothers, cousins cousins, jam jam, and jelly jelly. (TGST 31)

The love laws are not broken impulsively; rather, the choice was quite political. Transgression serves as an opportunity to register discomfort with the social order that has silenced the powerless. In *TMUH*, Anjum and Tilo transgress the boundaries of love laws by

nurturing the orphaned Zainab and Miss Jabeen. In a world which is filled with brutality, war, cruelty and divisive social norms, the act of Anjum and Tilo symbolises the power of love. Anjum, who is a transgender person, yearns to be a mother and loves her Zainab with the affection she did not receive in her own childhood. Her connection with Zainab defies the social boundaries set around motherhood. Similarly, Tilo who chooses to love and protect Miss Jabeen despite her own complicated situation establishes her as a human who could love even after the dehumanising effects of social and political forces. Love, here, becomes an assertion of individual identity and a symbol of personal rebellion.

Transgression serves as a crucial tool for marginalized individuals, allowing them to express their dissatisfaction with the injustices inflicted by those in authority. Arundhati Roy employs this technique as a means of shock, encouraging her audience to reconsider issues of limitation and the history imposed upon them. Through such acts, she believes that the marginalized can reveal the oppressive aspects of history and traditions.

The depiction of Khwabgah and its cultural practices illustrates an empowering history for its inhabitants. ‘The Sound and Light show’ at the Red Fort, along with Ustad Kulsoom Bi’s assertion that this is a government-approved version of history, highlights the concept of state-sponsored cultural erasure. Consequently, a transgressive act not only affirms individual identity but also the cultural identity of an entire group.

These acts facilitate a critical examination of present social conditions and suggest pathways for social and cultural change. For instance, Chacko’s brand of Communism is criticized as a system of exploitation. While Communism claims to support marginalized groups, it has proven inadequate in the context of India, especially against the backdrop of the caste system, which illustrates that such government systems can be just as corrupt and oppressive as any authoritarian regime.

Transgression acts as a challenge to social stagnation that renders the marginalized voiceless. When oppression is wielded as a tool by the powerful, disobedience becomes the means for the powerless to reclaim their voice. Although Roy does not promise a positive outcome from transgression, she portrays it as essential, as it provides a way to react against the injustices perpetrated by those in power. Transgression enables marginalized individuals to affirm their identities, resist oppressive forces, and advocate for a more inclusive and authentic society. It is an important act of rebellion, reclamation, and hope—challenging the status quo and paving the way for social change. Roy's narratives emphasize that without transgression, societal stagnation continues, and true progress remains out of reach. Thus, transgression is portrayed as an act of courage and a vital step toward breaking free from the constraints of conformity and injustice.

Works Cited:

Aristotle's Poetics: Translated, with Introduction and Notes, by C.D.C. Reeve- 1998 page-4

Durkheim, Emile. *The Division of Labour in Society*. New York: free Press, 1964. Print.

—. *The Rules of Sociological Method*. Trans. W. D. Halls. New York: The Free Press, 1982. Print.

Foust, Christina R. *Transgression as a Mode of Resistance: Rethinking Social Movement in an Era of Corporate Globalization*. Maryland: Lexington Books, 2010. Print.

Jenks, Chris. *Transgression*. London: Routledge, 2003. Print.

Roy, Arundhati. *The God of Small Things*. New Delhi: Penguin Books, 2002. Print.

—. *The Ministry of Utmost Happiness*. Haryana: Penguin Random House India, 2017. Print.